

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE APPLICATION OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE
INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**Khakberdiev Nurali Salakhiddinovich**Deputy head of the Department of Coordination of Special Operations
of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, lieutenant colonel.<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17497257>

Abstract. *The following areas of advanced foreign experience in ensuring the service activities of internal affairs officers were considered: the system of selection based on open and closed competitive examinations in the formation of personnel of internal affairs bodies, the practice of filling leadership positions in internal affairs bodies through elections, work on providing personnel aimed at training reserve personnel from among promising young people, the system of protecting the interests of internal affairs officers through trade unions. Also, the prospects for applying this positive experience in the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan were determined.*

Keywords: *internal affairs body, law, principle, selection, leadership position, employee, professional training.*

The effectiveness of the activities of the Internal Affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan directly depends on the quality of its employees. Therefore, high requirements are imposed on candidates for admission to the internal affairs bodies, since an employee of the internal affairs body has great powers and his actions affect both the freedom of the individual and the interests of the state. Unlike employees of many other institutions, employees of the internal affairs body are not considered a separate territorial or sectoral unit of the state, but rather as specific and general representatives of the state. In addition, the service of the internal affairs bodies is associated with constant stress and danger.

Officially, the most important principle in the recruitment of police officers is the principle of "equal opportunity", proclaimed during the French Revolution in 1789. According to this principle, all citizens have equal rights to occupy state and municipal positions, provided they possess the necessary abilities and individual qualities. This principle is especially clearly reflected in US legislation: The Civil Rights Act of 1964, The Age Discrimination in Employment Act of 1967, and The Rehabilitation Act of 1973¹.

In particular, the legal basis of "equal rights" in the USA uses two approaches: protection against discrimination against citizens based on certain criteria (skin color, nationality, religion); legally prohibiting police authorities from administering discriminatory tests on citizens.

The US government has developed and is implementing a number of programs to ensure the selection of high-quality candidates in accordance with applicable legal requirements. The essence of these programs is as follows:

a) The Ministry of Internal Affairs offers specialized courses and training for members of minority groups to provide effective assistance in preparing for the selection process;

¹ <https://www.archives.gov/milestone-documents/civil-rights-act>

b) a group of experienced experts, paid and financed by private foundations, will conduct additional training for police academy teachers on the concept of "equal rights"².

In some countries, the public participates in staffing the services and divisions of the internal affairs bodies. According to T.M. Zanina and K.D. Rydchenko, almost all states in the USA have established independent civil services (commissions) that are engaged in the recruitment, selection and even appointment of police officers to some non-elected positions at the rank of ordinary and junior management. These associations also have the right to recommend police officers to senior management positions. Members of the commission conduct certification, consider complaints about the service process, monitor disciplinary issues, and monitor social and pension issues. The establishment of commissions falls within the competence of the relevant territorial head, and the composition of the commission cannot be changed for a period established by the charter of its activities³.

On the basis of elections, leadership positions of internal affairs bodies are mainly filled, but this is done only in some countries. For example, in Switzerland, cantonal police chiefs and their deputies are elected, while in the United States, municipal police chiefs and sheriffs are elected, who represent the police authorities in rural and rural areas.

However, the main method of filling the staff of the internal affairs bodies is the selection method. This method is considered the best, as it provides equal opportunities for candidates, guarantees fairness and helps reduce the possibility of abuse. Information about the competition, its location, terms, procedure, number of vacant positions and basic requirements for candidates is provided in advance through departmental publications and the media (including the Internet).

As a positive experience in the field of appointment, one can cite the practice of the People's Republic of China. There, information about the appointment of a certain employee to a leadership position is published in the media and the global Internet. As S.A. Zhbanova rightly noted, as a result, citizens or other police officers, since this information is also posted on the internal electronic network of the Chinese police, usually within two weeks after the announcement of the expected appointment, have the opportunity to make an official statement about information that may interfere with their future appointment to the position⁴.

It is characteristic of many developed foreign countries that the process of replenishing and transferring police personnel is associated with the training of personnel. Here, "there is an international uniformity of national educational standards and partial and complete diversification of professional training models, as well as the improvement of the technological basis of training."

Thus, appointment to almost all positions (except for the top command structure), promotion of police officers and transfer from one department to another are usually determined by the successful completion of a two-stage advanced training course: study at a specialized educational institution and internship in an existing territorial internal affairs body⁵.

² Закатов В.В. Профессиональная подготовка сотрудников полиции за рубежом: особенности и тенденции развития // Балтийский гуманитарный журнал. 2017. Т. 6. № 4(21).

³ Занина Т.М., Рыдченко К.Д. Перспективы учета общественного мнения в ходе формирования кадрового состава полиции // Вестник Воронежского института ФСИН России. 2016. № 4

⁴ Жбанова С.А. Опыт зарубежных стран по подготовке кадров подразделений полиции // Научный вестник Орловского юридического института МВД России имени В.В. Лукьянова. 2017. № 1(70).

⁵ <https://www.iawp.org/about-the-IAWP>

After completing the training, police officers sign contracts for a fixed term of service (usually from three to five years) and can be re-taken. These contracts usually determine the salary level of various categories of police officers, additional payment for overtime, night bonuses, payment for seniority, as well as working hours and the specific features of the application and appeal of disciplinary measures for a particular position⁶.

In general, as a result of comparing the experience of working with employees of the Internal Affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan and police officers of many foreign countries, as well as the state and directions of their service activities, a number of conclusions and general theoretical aspects can be distinguished. First, it is clear that there are no significant differences in the activities of various law enforcement systems in many positions. Employees of law enforcement bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan have almost the same working days as Western police officers. We are talking about the length of the working day established by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan (although in practice it is often extended). Both in the Republic of Uzbekistan and in other countries, the need to limit the participation of employees in political life is recognized and confirmed by legislation, prohibiting the organization and participation in strikes, as well as holding multiple jobs, with the exception of some areas (science, education and art). The goals, scope of tasks and functions of law enforcement bodies are almost the same (taking into account the specific conditions of each country).

At the same time, there are also differences in the organization of work with law enforcement officers and the management of their service activities in Uzbekistan and other countries. Thus, in foreign countries, more democratic relations are observed between higher-ranking officials and their subordinates in the police than in the internal affairs departments of our country, although the legislation of Western countries has established a more strict system of subordination relations within the police than in other branches of the civil service⁷. However, the head of a police department usually only recommends or advises a subordinate employee to perform a certain action, but the employee has the opportunity to act on his own initiative. At the same time, each employee is personally responsible. If an employee does not listen to the advice of the head, the head does not bear any responsibility for the misconduct of his subordinate. In the internal affairs departments of the Republic of Uzbekistan, on the contrary, the head is responsible for maintaining discipline between the head and his subordinates, which requires subordinates to unconditionally carry out the orders of the head (with the exception of illegal orders).

In developed countries, police officers enjoy greater legal and social protection due to the active activities of police unions and associations.

In the internal affairs bodies of Uzbekistan, unlike the police structures of Western countries, alternative ways of promoting employees to higher levels of service are only discussed.

Studying the experience of organizing and managing police forces in foreign countries allows us to conclude that the system of managing the activities of officers in developed Western countries is much more advanced.

In clarifying the specifics of legal regulation and police management practice, we emphasize that the main goal and task here is to turn the police into a reliable tool for protecting

⁶ <https://www.theiacp.org/about-iacp>

⁷ <https://www.archives.gov/milestone-documents/civil-rights-act>

the existing state and the rule of law. Indeed, it is from this point of view that we should evaluate the appropriate social status of law enforcement officers and a set of measures to ensure their professional activities. It is also noted that the system of staffing and transfer of personnel in the police apparatus in developed foreign countries is also highly effective. The selection method, which is of primary importance in the formation of the personnel base, allows you to select the most worthy personnel from a large number of candidates by checking their qualities in various ways. At the same time, the use of the appointment method to fill vacant senior management positions allows, from the point of view of management, to give priority in management to those persons who can effectively carry out official doctrinal assignments.

Taking into account the above, it is very useful to study international experience in the context of completing the reform of the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is necessary to study in depth and implement in practice the elements of the management system of internal affairs bodies employees, as well as measures to ensure their service activities in developed countries. In this regard, such advanced issues as the formation of personnel of internal affairs bodies on a competitive basis, rotation of personnel, and protection of the interests of internal affairs bodies employees through trade unions deserve great attention. Studying, generalizing and, to the extent possible, implementing in practice the experience of working with internal affairs bodies employees of foreign countries is an important step towards further professionalization, democratization and humanization of internal affairs bodies, and strengthens the foundations for ensuring the service activities of their employees.

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